

Relation Between Lorentz Boost and Noncollective Momentum Conservation in 1D Reflection/Refraction?

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In this note we investigate the possibility of obtaining the Lorentz boost transformation matrix by considering the conservation of non-collective momentum in one dimensional (1D) photon reflection-refraction. One may consider the problem of 1D reflection/refraction with a stationary n_1/n_2 interface. We choose $n_1=1$ here. We suggest that one may use the usual conservation of square root flux and momentum weighted by square root flux (1). The latter is a kind of conservation of momentum. The question is what happens if the interface moves? We suggest that if one had a photon confined to a box, then its energy, w , would contribute to rest mass. If the box were moving, then this rest mass should contribute to momentum in the usual way $w' v$, i.e. a kind of energy flux. At this point, we assume that the form of the Lorentz boost is unknown. Already in the non-moving medium scenario, one may postulate a function $\exp(ikx \pm iwt)$ such that d/dx partial brings down k and d/dt partial, $\pm w$. At this point there is no preference for $+$ or $-$.

We suggest that a moving interface gives the appearance of photons on each side of the interface as belonging to bodies moving with velocity v (in the x direction).

By writing a conservation of noncollective momentum for the moving interface picture, one may postulate the form of a function $\exp(-iwt+ikx)$ with the minus sign being required so that collective momentum is subtracted from the overall momentum. Thus one chooses $\exp(ikx-iwt)$. Furthermore, one may create a 2×2 matrix with $a_{11}=g$ and $a_{21}=g v$ where $g(v)$ is unknown. If one postulates that $kx-wt$ is an invariant because it is linked with probability which should depend on a frame of reference, then one may see that there is an unusual metric present. This metric is represented by the 2×2 matrix with a first row of $(1,0)$ and a second of $(0,-1)$ If one makes the transformation matrix Hermitian and uses the metric, then Identity= Transformation matrix * Metrixc matrix * Transforamtion matrix (as a kind of unitary approach) then: $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/aa}$ where a has units of a velocity and is frame independent. One may suggest $a=c$, the speed of light in a vacuum.

One Dimensional Photon Reflection-Refraction

One dimensional photon reflection-refraction is a probabilistic problem which exists in the macroscopic world. Physically one may try to express a conservation of probability in terms of fluxes, i.e. the number of photons per second because photon speed changes with a change in index of refraction. We consider $n_1=1$ and $n_2>n_1$ with n_1 present for $x<0$ and $x=0$, $x>0$ representing n_2 . We write AA, BB, CC for the fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted 1-D photons (because flux is positive) with energy being the same for all. The conservation of probability (or energy if one multiplies by w , the photon energy is):

$$k AA = |k| BB + k_2 CC \quad \text{where } k_2=n_2k \quad ((1)) \quad \text{because flux= probability * speed of photon}$$

$$\text{and } w=kc= (n_2k) c/n_2$$

If one sets $A=1$, then there are two unknowns B, C , but one equation. One may immediately notice a difference of squares:

$$k(A-B) = k^2 C \quad ((2))$$

and break ((2)) into two equations: $A+B=C$ ((3a)) and $kA-kB = k^2 C$ ((3b))

One may proceed to solve for B/A and C/A as done in (1).

Mathematically, one may consider time and spatial generators d/dt partial and d/dx partial and introduce a function $\exp(ikx \pm i\omega t)$ so that ((3a)):

$$d/dt (A+B) \text{ partial} = d/dt C \text{ partial} \text{ because } \omega \text{ is the same for incident/reflected/refracted photons} \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{and } d/dx (A+B) \text{ partial} = d/dx C \text{ partial} \quad ((4b))$$

At this point it is not clear if one should use $kx-\omega t$ or $kx+\omega t$, but for the 1D problem with a fixed n_1-n_2 this is not really an issue as one does not really need $\exp(ikx \pm i\omega t)$ in the first place.

The Question of a Moving Interface

One may ask: What should be done if the n_1-n_2 interface moves (say to the right in along the x axis)? We first note that if one has a photon in a box (moving in 1D and reflecting), then its energy is like rest mass energy. If the box moves, the photon energy (acting like box rest mass) transforms to w' (the explicit form we assume is unknown at present) and there is a momentum or energy flux contribution of $w'v$. We call this collective momentum because the photon itself has momentum k' (transformed again in an unknown manner). We suggest that a moving interface is like to moving boxes, one with $n_1=1$ and the other n_2 . Thus, there should be collective momentum in each.

In the incident-reflection-refraction problem with no interface motion, one equates momenta with A, B, C weights. If for the moving frame, one subtracts collective momentum from full momentum, one may argue that this conservation is of the same form as the rest interface one.

The collective momenta are: $w(\text{incident})'v$, $w(\text{reflected})'v$ and $w(\text{refracted})'v$, all along x . ((5))

The following conservation equation should exist:

$$A\{k(\text{incident})' - w(\text{incident})'v\} + B\{k(\text{reflected})' - w(\text{reflected})'v\} = C\{k(\text{refracted})' - w(\text{refracted})'v\} \quad ((6))$$

At the same time, one may retain $A+B=C$ as conservation of probability.

At this point, one may notice the natural minus sign in front of energy. If one wishes to write ((6)) in terms of an eigenfunction of the temporal and spatial generators, d/dt partial and d/dx partial, then one may use $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$. This function is associated with a kind of probability as $AA = (A\exp(-i\omega t+ikx)) * (A\exp(-i\omega t+ikx))$. Thus, we postulate that $-\omega t+kx$ should be invariant, i.e. have the same value in the rest interface versus moving interface scenarios.

First, however, one may find information about the transformation of energies and momenta from the noncollective momentum conservation equation ((6)).

In the rest interface situation, one only needs d/dx to obtain k , but for ((6)) and $\exp(-i\omega' t' + ik' x')$ one requires d/dx' and d/dt' , thus:

Ultimately ((6)) and $A+B=C$ must yield the same probabilities as $kA-kB=k^2C$ with $A+B=C$.

Thus:

$$d/dx = dx'/dx d/dx' + dt'/dx d/dt' \quad ((7))$$

Examining ((6)) yields: $dx'/dx = g(v)$ and $dt'/dx = v g(v)$ ((8)), where $g(v)$ is some unknown function of v .

This leads to a matrix transformation:

$$\begin{matrix} |x'| & = & |g & b1| & |x| \\ |t'| & & |gv & b2| & |t| \end{matrix} \quad ((8))$$

At first it may seem that there are too many unknowns in ((8)), namely $g(v)$, $b1(v)$ and $b2(v)$. If, however, one considers $\exp(-i\omega t+ikx)$ with $-\omega t+kx$ as an invariant because probability does not transform and one may argue that this function is connected with probability, then one notices that a certain metric is being used, namely:

$$\begin{matrix} (k,\omega) & | & 1 & 0 & | & x| \\ & & | & 0 & -1 & | & t| \end{matrix} \quad ((9))$$

Usually, one would require a unitary matrix to keep the modulus of a dot product constant, but with the metric of ((9)), one may consider $b1=gv$ and $b2=g$. Then:

$$\text{Identity Matrix} = \begin{matrix} | & g & gv & | & | & 1 & 0 & | & g & gv & | \\ & | & gv & g & | & 0 & -1 & | & gv & g & | \end{matrix} \quad ((10))$$

This yields: $gg(1-vv) = 1$ or $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/aa}$ where a is a constant with units of velocity. This velocity should be frame independent and so the speed of light seems like a good candidate because it follows from parameters in Maxwell's EM equations which are of the same form in different boosted frames. ($c= 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0\mu_0}$).

Thus, we argue that one may obtain the Lorentz boost matrix shown in ((10)) by considering conservation of noncollective momentum using square root of flux weights. If $\int dx A^*A$ is a constant, then $dx \rightarrow dx/g$ so $A \rightarrow \sqrt{g} A$, but this weight applies to A,B,C and so cancels from the conservation equation.

Example

As a specific example, of the above ideas we note that:

$$M = d/dx \exp(-i\omega t + ik_2 x) = ik_2 \exp(-i\omega t + ik_2 x)$$

One may show explicitly that $-w' t' + k' x' = -\omega t + kx$ using the transformation matrix of ((10)).

$d/dx = g(d/dx' + v d/dt')$ partial so $M = g(k_2' - v \omega_2') = k_2'(1 - v/n')$ g where n' is index of refraction in the frame watching the interface move. Here k_2 is the momentum in the n_2 medium.

$$k_2' = gk_2 + gv\omega_2 = gk_2 (1 + v/n) \quad \text{Thus: } M = gk_2 (n + v)/n \cdot n(1 - vv) / (n + v) = k_2$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may obtain the Lorentz boost matrix by considering one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon if one insists that one have square root flux probability weighted conservation of noncollective momentum in a frame in which the interface moves with velocity v . If a photon were trapped in a box, its energy would contribute to the rest mass of the box. If the box is seen to move, then a collective momentum of photon energy $'$, multiplied by v should exist. This is a collective type of momentum separate from the overall momentum k' . Here $'$ represents the energy and momentum seen in the frame in which the interface moves with v . We suggest that a moving interface is like two moving boxes, one with $n_1=1$ and the other with n_2 .

Thus, we suggest that: $A\{k \text{ incident } ' + v (-w \text{ incident } ')\} + B\{k \text{ reflected } ' - v w \text{ reflected } '\} = C\{k \text{ refracted } ' - v w \text{ refracted } '\}$ may be linked to: $d/dx = dt'/dt d/dt' \text{ partial} + d/dx' dx'/dt$ and that $a_{11}=g$ and $a_{12}=gv$ for a 2×2 matrix. Here one assumes that derivatives act on $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$. The minus sign appears in front of w because this collective piece must be subtracted in the noncollective momentum conservation equation. If $-\omega t + kx$ is an invariant, one sees that there is a metric matrix with a first row of $(1,0)$ and a second row of $(0,-1)$. One may make the transformation matrix Hermitian so that $a_{12}=gv$ and $a_{22}=g$. Here g is unknown. Using: identity = 2×2 matrix * Metric matrix * 2×2 matrix, one finds that $g = 1/\sqrt{1 - vv/aa}$. Here a has units of velocity and is frame independent. One may suggest c , speed of light in a vacuum as a candidate for a .

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change